

THE MEXICAN AMERICAN ELDEST

DAUGHTER EXPERIENCE

by

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Abstract

In a Latinx traditional household, the prevalence of larger families often results in a higher likelihood of children assuming parentified roles, with the eldest daughter bearing the role. The background research will discuss what parentification is, which is when a child takes on the parenting role over their parent(s) and/or siblings, how it affects the child, and what the eldest daughters are saying on TikTok. The Mexican American Eldest Daughter Experience (MAEDE) adds knowledge to the lack of academic research for these daughters, but on social media, the eldest daughters are being vocal about their experiences. The MAEDE's method is photovoice, in which the participants, who study at Cal State Fullerton, take five photographs of their day-to-day experiences as their role and write a narrative paragraph about what they have captured. They presented the photovoice to the investigator so that the recordings could be posted on YouTube for public access. When analyzing, it was found that they are being parentified, which gives them responsibilities and essential roles; due to their culture's core value of familismo, they feel pressure and put others before themselves. The themes indicate that the eldest daughter's role is integral to the family, reveal their challenges, and express the effects of being parentified.

Key Words: eldest daughter, photovoice, parentification, Mexican American, familismo

The Mexican American Eldest Daughter Experience

Growing up in a Mexican family and community, I have seen and been confided in how females feel about their place in their family. My search was started due to the number of eldest daughters of all ages who have confided in me about what they are going through at home and within their familial relationships. I first learned about what these daughters are going through, which is called parentification, and other aspects of their experience through TikTok. I tried to learn more about the experience of the Mexican American eldest daughter in academia, but there was a lack of focused research about what they experience and how it affects them. This connected to a prior class with my mentor, where he stated that we have to historicize our community because no one else will. The research I wanted and am doing was to interact with the community to try to record their first-hand experience. Photovoice is the methodology that I am using to visually represent what these daughters experience, but it also allows the daughters to reflect on what they have gone through. With the gap in research for Mexican American eldest daughters, the participants will be historicizing their experiences of their parentified role with several roles and responsibilities, and due to their core value of familismo, they are having a codependent relationship and feeling unconscious pressure through photovoice.

Background

What Is Parentification? The idea of parentification was brought to my attention by a Tiktok from user @milypsicologia, where Mily Gomez explains that the eldest daughter is “assigned” as another parental figure in the household because the parents are working and they are not able to fulfill everything in their household, like caring for their children. Gomez continues that the caregiver role continues into adulthood, and the “role causes a lot of stress, a lot of worry. We have this overdeveloped sense of responsibility that we can’t get rid of.” What Gomez describes

is called parentification with an unconscious pressure to continue into adulthood, and this has been a topic that has been trending, which even Latina singer Becky G has spoken out about. What it means to be parentified is to have an "inverted child-parent relationship" (Sang et al., 253). The children are doing more than just chores and have assumed an adult role in the household (Engelhardt, 45). There are four different types of relationships that children have when they are parentified, which are

“(a) spousal role vis-a-vis parents—the child taking on spousal roles to the parent, (b) parental role vis-a-vis parents—the child acting as a parent to the parent, (c) parental role vis-a-vis siblings—the child taking on a parental role to the siblings, and (d) nonspecific adult role-taking—includes doing household chores for other family members” (Sang Et al., 254).

For this project, the daughters that are participating will be shown in their photovoices (c) and (d). The parentified role is created in different ways, like explicitly entrusting the child, but also because the child can see that there is a need that they can fill (Engelhardt, 46). Furthermore, in a TikTok by Randi, @feelingrandi78, she brings up the good point that when being the eldest in a household and given the role of caretaker, the eldest is no longer seen as a child but as a caregiver. The responsibilities are given to them because the young children are not capable of completing what the eldest is able to do (@feelingrandi78). Some of the roles that the eldest daughter plays are financial advisor, travel agent, event planner, tutor, and counselor, which are described on TikTok by Nikita Fernandes, @nikita_fernandes.

Why Are Children Being Parentified? In “Parentification, Substance Use, and Sex Among Adolescent Daughters from Ethnic Minority Families,” Sang et al. explain that children become parentified when the family is going through “stressors,” which in turn makes the parents turn to

the children for support but also makes them the support for their sibling(s) (252). Culture and gender are factors in determining which child gets parentified, and the daughter is usually the one who is burdened (Sang et al., 254). Valenzuela names the experience "eldest daughter syndrome" because they are the only ones subjected to this role; it will not be given to the eldest son. This idea is reaffirmed by the TikTok user Jenny Ortega, @Jennyfromla805, where she states that she has not "met an older brother taking on the role of what a girl has to do." Even though the daughter has an integral role in the household, there is greater celebration of male births compared to females, and this was noticed by Frances in *The Migrant Daughter: Coming of Age as a Mexican American Woman*, which was an oral history based on a book by oral historian Mario Garcia on Frances Esquibel Tywoniak (33). The daughter is supposed to be nurturing, and the son is supposed to be dominant (Longoria et al., 1). In the Mexican American family, the women are expected to "consider their own wants, desires, and needs as secondary to the needs of the family, particularly the male members of the family" (Longoria et al., 1). The reason why the Mexican American daughters take on this "nurturance and care" role is because they feel the need to repay their parents for their sacrifices (Longoria et al., 3).

What Are The Effects? In a study of daughters being parentified in the mother-daughter relationship, they found that the daughters became "self silencing" in order to appease their mother (Goldner et al., 170). "Self-silencing" means that they suppress their "thoughts and feelings within the context of a relationship" (Goldner et al., 165). When children enter this cycle of parentification and show "self silencing" behavior, they end up with a "low sense of self efficacy and self-esteem" (Goldner et al., 166). This behavior is seen in "Dutiful Daughter" by Diana Lopez, where Juanita is living with her parents, and her parents do not want her to move out until she gets married (Lopez, 153). She was thinking of going to college, but her parents

discouraged her because they implied she was not smart enough and that college is “dangerous, especially for young women like you” (Lopez, 144). Like Goldner et al. claimed in their article, the parentified child becomes self silencing, which makes her get lost in appeasing her parents over her wants and needs. She needed to be the dutiful daughter by following what her parents wanted her to do, but in the end, she came to realize that she could do what she wanted. The idea of self silencing is further developed in the theme section, and it can be further developed into another term.

How Common Is Parentification? Looking into the different family sizes in the United States, Latinos are the group with the highest rates of having a big family (Livingston). For example, 20% of Hispanic mothers ages 40–44 have four or more children (Livingston). For Mexicans, the median household income in the U.S. is \$59,200, which means that if parents want to support a big family, they would need to constantly be working (Moslimani et al.). This in turn will put children at risk for parentification because the parents are working and there needs to be someone at home to be the authority figure over the children, and that will go to the eldest daughter, just like Valenzuela and @Jennyfromla805 stated.

Methods

The eldest Mexican American daughter is from a low-researched area, so providing video-recorded accounts of photovoice is able to create patterns and emphasize the phenomena of their role, like parentification (Valenzuela). This project uses a different methodology from the research within Mexican American families. This project was approved by the CalState Fullerton Institutional Review Board due to the involvement of human participants. The participants of this project are the eldest daughters who are Mexican American, who are 18–25 years old, attend CalState Fullerton, and live with their families. They were recruited through flyers posted around

campus and word-of-mouth. The participants were given information on what a photovoice is, how to accomplish it, and useful examples of what others have done with their photovoices. They had to sign a consent form. Once they completed their photovoices, they had to meet with the investigator to film them presenting their photos and saying their description via Zoom. The presentations were uploaded to the MAEDE YouTube channel to spread awareness of these women's experiences and create a community.

Who are the participants?

Jacqueline is a twenty-year-old first-generation Cal State Fullerton student in her fourth year.

She is living with both of her parents and is the eldest sister to a brother and a sister.

Michelle is a twenty-year-old first-generation Cal State Fullerton student in her fourth year. She is living with both of her parents and is the eldest sister, but she has three older brothers.

Odalys G. is a twenty-year-old first-generation Cal State Fullerton student in her third year. She is living with both of her parents and is the eldest sister of two sisters.

Themes

After the presentations of their photovoices, I began to see common themes among the photos and the descriptions. They experience parentification, which gives them roles and responsibilities, and due to familismo, they are having codependent relationships and feeling unconscious pressures.

Parentification/Parentified Role. The parentified role can look different for people because it depends on the dynamics of the household and cultural values. Michelle is the sibling that was parentified due to her gender. In Photo 2.1, she took a photo of her kitchen because, as she explains in her description, this is part of her role in her household.

Photo 2.1:

“As the daughter of immigrant parents, my parents have always been traditional, especially my mother. She believed that it was necessary for a daughter to learn how to serve her brothers and learn how to cook. When I was ten

years old, she began teaching me in the kitchen. One day, I was trying to flip tortillas with a spatula because I was afraid of the flame. She took the spatula away and told me to flip them with my hands. I burned myself and she said it was okay because “las mujeres deben aprender como aguantar la lumbre.” She taught me how to become responsible and independent.”

- Michelle

Michelle explains how her immigrant parents being traditional and having gender roles is a common view in Mexican immigrant households because they are the roles the parents learn from their patriarchal native country. Part of Michelle’s parentification was that her mother thrust this role onto her at a very young age, just like what Sarah Sloat described in her article, “The Plight of the Eldest Daughter,” about how the role is “imposed by family members.” Michelle had to take on the traditional role of the female serving males, in this case her brothers, and learn how to manage the kitchen.

Parentifying a child allows for the child to take on roles and responsibilities that seem to be given to adults, but that is a part of being parentified; the child becomes another adult in the

household that has a higher quantity of responsibilities as well as elevating the level of the kind of responsibilities. Jacqueline and Odalys had a very similar experience by being the designated translators for their Spanish-speaking parents, but in academic wording, these daughters are language brokers. Odalys took a photo of papers with envelopes displaying this (Photo 3.4), and Jacqueline took photos of envelopes symbolizing the papers she would have to read (Photo 1.1).

Photo 3.4

“All our family documents consist of English, which makes it difficult for my parents to understand what is going on. As such I help out my family by being the designated translator, especially since I have my biliteracy seal in Spanish. Even though my other sibling speaks and understands Spanish, my parents unconsciously bring all documents to me even when I am busy. I must make myself not busy.” - Odalys

Photo 1.1

“I took a picture of these envelopes because as the eldest Mexican American Daughter growing up I would have the responsibility of translating many documents for my parents because they do not speak English well. Everytime I look at envelopes it reminds me of this responsibility that I have up to this day. It sometimes can be challenging for me because sometimes I know words in English but do not know what they are in Spanish.” - Jacqueline

Language brokering is the “act of interpreting within immigrant families by children, adolescents, and adult children for their parents” and others (Morales et al.). Jacqueline and Odalys acknowledge that even to this day, their parents still bring their papers to them and not their siblings. In “Language Brokering Among Mexican-Immigrant Families” by Morales et al., it states that the gender that tends to become one for the family is female, but in family dynamics, the language broker would be the oldest. In this instance, it is the eldest daughter in their Mexican family household. The envelopes are the symbol for these daughters of the adult role of language brokering because they are probably the brokers at different places, like meetings, doctor appointments, or banks.

The parentified role for these eldest daughters that they also have to take on is being another parent for their family members. Since these daughters are the children of immigrants, their parents are navigating a new country that uses a language they speak very little or none. As the eldest daughter grows up in the country, they start to know the language, so they should be able to navigate the rest of the country. The daughter then becomes a parent in the sense that they are someone the siblings or younger relatives can look to for knowledge in any aspect. Michelle shows this by taking a photo of herself helping her niece do homework (Photo 2.4), and Jacqueline takes a similar photo of herself helping her sibling (Photo 1.3).

Photo 2.4

“As a first generation student, I have learned the value of education and the significance it holds. I want to ensure that my family understands its importance too. Although my niece is an eighth grader, I want to capture her attention with the wonders of higher education. I want her to not only pursue it, but to fall in love

with it. Just like I did. Most of my evenings are spent helping her out with homework before I can commence my own. Her success is important to me.” - Michelle’s Description

“I want to ensure she (niece) is successful. I want to ensure she has all the help she needs because I know growing up, I didn’t have that much help. Meaning that I would have to rely on myself or a couple of my friends to get the help that I needed, so I want to be that resource for her.” - Michelle when presenting

Photo 1.3

“As the eldest daughter I have taken a lot of responsibilities and another one is seen in this picture. I also have to help out my siblings with their school work whenever they are confused. I place that responsibility upon myself because when I was younger I struggled through school whenever I did not know something, especially when I was in elementary school because I did not know how to do it. I do not want my siblings to go through the same

things so I help them out.” - Jacqueline

Both of these daughters struggled in the education system, but they did not have someone to look to. Now, the eldest daughters feel the responsibility to be the source of information and help for their family members, like Michelle for her niece and Jacqueline for her siblings. Michelle and Jacqueline are building their families social and cultural capital as first-generation college students (Luedke, 1045). They are bringing new information about "planting seeds to transform cultural capital valued in higher education into funds of knowledge within their families over time" (Luedke, 1045). When Michelle and Jacqueline were struggling, they had to find out where they could get help, and they brought them back for their family members. They are the

navigators in place that they are getting to know, but they need to be the ones to actively seek out what they need. This is an adult role relying on the shoulders of the eldest.

Familismo and Codependent Relationships In the presentations of their photovoices, it is very apparent that the daughters value and have strong relationships with their families, which is called familismo (Taylor et al.). Familismo is a core belief that is part of Mexican culture (Taylor et al.). But it does seem that this value creates a codependent relationship with their families. The term co-dependency is mainly used in research for relationships with a person with alcoholism and their loved ones, but the basic meaning of the term can describe the relationship the daughters seem to have with their families. What the term means is “when one person believes it’s their job to save another person by attending to all of their needs. A codependent person builds their identity around this purpose and takes on a self-sacrificial role in the relationship” (“Codependency: Signs, Causes, and Help”). The codependency in relationships within family dynamics is different from how it is described in relationships with an alcoholic or romantic partner. In a codependent relationship with an alcoholic, the other person can be enabling or so concentrated on the recovery of the person. In the aspect that I am using the term, the daughters are putting their family ahead of their needs due to their value of familiasmo. The daughters have the unconscious thoughts and pressure they need to put others before themselves. Odalys’ explains that there is a constant “unconconscious feeling of pressure” to always be available for her family. She took a photo of her driving because she now has a car to go to places, but she uses it to help her family, even if her parents tell her that it is okay if she has other things to do (Photo 3.1).

Photo 3.1

“There is always this unconscious feeling of pressure that I must take on the responsibility of an adult. Even if this means that I am tired, busy, or I just do not feel motivated to help out. Me having a car and being able to arrive home early signifies that I must push myself to support my family as much as possible.” - Odalys

This pressure that Odalys feels is part of her co-dependency on her family and also of how she values her family. Her family comes first, even if she has to put her needs to the side. This is the form of self silencing the daughters put upon themselves because they do not want to tell their parents how they feel due to that unconscious pressure.

Another example of familismo that the daughters present in their photovoices is the pressure to succeed and give back to their parents. In Jacqueline's Photo 1.5, she describes that she has started to work and is finally able to give back to her family, especially to her parents.

Photo 1.5

“This picture is just of a milkshake but for me it means much more than that. This is the first time I was able to treat my mom out with money that I had earned from my job. It was such a great feeling and this is one of the many great things about being the eldest daughter because now I can buy stuff for my parents and give back to them for all that they have done for me.” - Jacqueline

Just like Longoria et al. described, the daughters feel the need to repay their parents for their sacrifices in coming to a new country for more opportunities for themselves and their children

(Longoria et al., 3). But in Michelle's photovoice, familismo shows up in the form of trying to be successful through education for her family (Photo 2.3).

Photo 2.3

"Since elementary school, my parents would always emphasize how important and powerful education was. My mother would remind me to do my best because she never had the opportunity to finish her education due to her obligations. Therefore, I was her hope. I became a hope in my family and my

objective became clear. I needed to focus on my work and make my family proud. Failing was not an option and it still isn't. I can still feel the pressure on my shoulders. This need to become a role model. This need to make a change. This need to prove my worth as a Mexican American daughter. This need to prove to myself that I can do it." - Michelle

Since Michelle is the first generation, there is a need to accomplish higher education because she is the family's hope to change things around. The idea of succeeding is not just for Michelle herself but also for her family. This is familismo, and it can strengthen a person by giving them a purpose. Ayon et al. state that it is an "indicator of improved mental health" in the Latinx community, but this core value can create tendencies. It is a bit of a self-silencing tendency, but a better phase is prioritizing others because they are talking about what they are experiencing in this project and not staying silent. This is seen in Odalys Photo 3.2, where she is describing how she needs to sacrifice herself because she needs to put her family's needs first.

Photo 3.2

“I spend most of my day either at school, work, and/or in clubs on campus. Me being involved does not mean that I do not want to be home, but there is just no possibility for me to be at home in peace. There are always chores to get done, siblings to take care, errands to complete, and so much more. Even though I am constantly

told that I am not obliged to do anything, unconsciously I know that in my position I must set a standard and need to sacrifice myself.” - Odalys

Being loyal to the family is healthy, and prioritizing the family is a great core value, but the eldest daughters having the parentified role makes them overextend themselves to try to juggle their lives. This is described and seen in Jacqueline’s Photo 1.4.

Photo 1.4

“This is a picture of the steering wheel of my car. I took it because it reminds me of the responsibility that I have gained now that I am driving. I have to take my siblings to school or pick them up when my parents are busy. It does sometimes get a bit hard when I am tired and do not want to drive but it is something I can do to help out my parents.” - Jacqueline

They put it on themselves to keep playing the same role even if they are tired because they know that that is their duty. They are overextending themselves to their family, which is the negative side of prioritizing family, and the relationship becomes codependent.

Acknowledgements

There needs to be an acknowledgement that the parents are not to blame for what the eldest daughters experience because this is part of their culture's values of the female being the nurturer and their circumstances in a new country. The parents have taken what they know from their native country and are trying to build a family in a new country. Another acknowledgement is that the eldest daughter experience is being called eldest daughter syndrome, but I do not want to call what they experience a "syndrome," because it is more than a "group of signs and symptoms that occur together and characterize a particular abnormality or condition" ("Definition"). The eldest daughter is embedded in their culture, so it is not just a group of characteristics. An issue with the project is that this participant group is small, so there needs to be a more in- depth study dedicated to the Mexican American eldest daughter to give a much more comprehensive view. The last acknowledgement is that what the eldest daughter experiences is shared among different cultures, but where it differs for the Mexican American daughters is that the core value of familismo. The Mexican culture has a strong dedication to their family, and since they are in the United States, the daughters have other responsibilities and roles given to them due to their being the first generation.

Conclusion

The Mexican American eldest daughters experience parentification that gives them adult roles and responsibilities, and with their familismo values, the daughters begin to have a codependent relationship and prioritize the family. For further research, researchers need to make the distinction between the eldest daughter role and the eldest brother role to see the differences, if any. The videos will be on the Mexican American Edest Daughter Experience YouTube channel, so that the public has access. I hope that sharing their stories will help bring recognition

to the vital role that the eldest Mexican American daughter has within their household and give these strong women a platform to historize their experience.

Appendix 1: Jacqueline's Photovoice

Photo 1.1

"I took a picture of these envelopes because as the eldest Mexican American Daughter growing up I would have the responsibility of translating many documents for my parents because they do not speak English well. Everytime I look at envelopes it reminds me of this responsibility that I have up to this day. It sometimes can be challenging for me because sometimes I know words in English but do not know what they are in Spanish." - Jacqueline

Photo 1.2

"I also took a picture of the CSUF sign because this is a reminder of how I have had to navigate getting through college all by myself. None of my parents were able to continue their education due to their circumstances. I had to figure out everything from filling out the Fafsa to filling out college applications. However, this picture is also a reminder of me being a first-generation college student which is also an important accomplishment in my life." - Jacqueline

Photo 1.3

“As the eldest daughter I have taken a lot of responsibilities and another one is seen in this picture. I also have to help out my siblings with their school work whenever they are confused. I place that responsibility upon myself because when I was younger I struggled through school whenever I did not know something, especially when I was in elementary school because I did not know how to do it. I do not want my siblings to go through the same things so I help them out.” - Jacqueline

Photo 1.4

“This is a picture of the steering wheel of my car. I took it because it reminds me of the responsibility that I have gained now that I am driving. I have to take my siblings to school or pick them up when my parents are busy. It does sometimes get a bit hard when I am tired and do not want to drive but it is something I can do to help out my parents.” - Jacqueline

Photo 1.5

“This picture is just of a milkshake but for me it means much more than that. This is the first time I was able to treat my mom out with money that I had earned from my job. It was such a great feeling and this is one of the many great things about being the eldest daughter because now I can buy stuff for my parents and give back to them for all that they have done for me.” -

Jacqueline

Appendix 2: Michelle's Photovoice

Photo 2.1

“As the daughter of immigrant parents, my parents have always been traditional, especially my mother. She believed that it was necessary for a daughter to learn how to serve her brothers and learn how to cook. When I was ten years old, she began teaching me in the kitchen. One day, I was trying to flip tortillas with a spatula because I was afraid of the flame. She took the spatula away and told me to flip them with my hands. I burned myself and she said it was okay because “las mujeres deben aprender como aguantar la lumbre.” She taught me how to become responsible and independent.” - Michelle

Photo 2.2

“In a sense, I am quite old fashioned and I mainly find the cause of this to be my parents’ taste in music. My brothers and I grew up listening to their music all the time. The music mainly came in the form of cassette tapes and ,more recently, in CDs. Ever since I was twelve, I fell in love with this generation of music, both in Spanish and English. This crave for vintage music was born, and I have not stopped seeking for more of it. My music preference may seem odd to most, but my

	<p><i>parents taught me to appreciate the lost beauty of the older generation.” - Michelle</i></p>
<p>Photo 2.3</p>	<p><i>“Since elementary school, my parents would always emphasize how important and powerful education was. My mother would remind me to do my best because she never had the opportunity to finish her education due to her obligations. Therefore, I was her hope. I became a hope in my family and my objective became clear. I needed to focus on my work and make my family proud. Failing was not an option and it still isn’t. I can still feel the pressure on my shoulders. This need to become a role model. This need to make a change. This need to prove my worth as a Mexican American daughter. This need to prove to myself that I can do it.” - Michelle</i></p>

Photo 2.4

“As a first generation student, I have learned the value of education and the significance it holds. I want to ensure that my family understands its importance too. Although my niece is an eighth grader, I want to capture her attention with the wonders of higher education. I want her to not only pursue it, but to fall in love with it. Just like I did. Most of my evenings are spent helping her out with homework before I can commence my own. Her success is important to me.”

- Michelle

Photo 2.5

“One of the few places of comfort that I can find time for myself is the library. Its silence and solitude allows me to break free from my chaotic world. Where I can have time to myself and not be my family’s therapist for at least a day. It contains forms of escapism for me where I can delve into stories. My love for literature has kept me company throughout the years. Aside from books, my friends have helped me along the way too. Though I don’t have many, my friends have allowed me to form meaningful relationships where we can share our perspective of the world we each live in.”

- Michelle

Appendix 3: Odalys' Photovoice

Photo 3.1

"I am always given options in my life, but I never take on my own decision. There is always this unconscious feeling of pressure that I must take on the responsibility of an adult. Even if this means that I am tired, busy, or I just do not feel motivated to help out. Me having a car and being able to arrive home early signifies that I must push myself to support my family as much as possible." - Odalys

Photo 3.2

"I spend most of my day either at school, work, and/or in clubs on campus. Me being involved does not mean that I do not want to be home, but there is just no possibility for me to be at home in peace. There are always chores to get done, siblings to take care, errands to complete, and so much more. Even though I am constantly told that I am not obliged to do anything, unconsciously I know that in my position I must set a standard and need to sacrifice myself."

- Odalys

Photo 3.3

“Moving from high school to college was a big change in my life. I had to learn how to make friends and take initiative in classes. Three years later it has gotten a little easier but there is still a struggle in maintaining strong, lasting relationships. Especially, with my heavy involvement on campus I feel that it is even more difficult for me to maintain connections.”

- Odalys

Photo 3.4

“All our family documents consist of English, which makes it difficult for my parents to understand what is going on. As such I help out my family by being the designated translator, especially since I have my biliteracy seal in Spanish. Even though my other sibling speaks and understands Spanish, my parents unconsciously bring all documents to me even when I am busy. I must make myself not busy.” - Odalys

Photo 3.5

“Over the weekend, my family assumes that I do not have any other obligations I need to get done. Consequently, I must help out around the house when they are both at work. Though they have told me that if I am busy then I just need to let them know and everything will be find. Even so there is this obligation and pressure I feel in getting things done to demonstrate my efficiency as the eldest daughter. I can take on multiple tasks no matter the aftermath.”

- Odalys

Appendix 4: The Mexican American Eldest Daughter Experience YouTube Chanel

This is the link to the YouTube chanel where the videos were posted:

<https://www.youtube.com/@TheMAEDEXperience>

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